

Understanding Consumer Purchase Intention in a Blockchain Technology for Food Traceability and Transparency context

Jen-Yin Yeh
Department of Automation
and Management
National Pingtung University
Pingtung City, Taiwan
jenyiny@gmail.com

Ssu-Chi Liao
Department of Automation
and Management
National Pingtung University
Pingtung, Taiwan
judyl2342009@gmail.com

Yu-Ting Wang
Department of Automation
and Management
National Pingtung University
Pingtung, Taiwan
yutingw226@gmail.com

Yi-Jia Chen
Department of Automation
and Management
National Pingtung University
Pingtung, Taiwan
jiaga0108@gmail.com

ABSTRACT-From being associated with the financial services primarily, blockchain is now affecting other industries as well. Blockchain is attracting interest as a way to track and monitor food through the supply network, ensuring its origin. Consumers are increasingly demanding to know where their purchases come from and how they are made. In food industry, consumers can confirm the provenance of their purchases by blockchain. Despite some blockchain research on innovation adoption in fintech contexts, little is known about how consumers evaluate blockchain in food traceability and transparency. This study explores consumers' motivations to purchase food with blockchain code and takes the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology 2 (UTAUT2) as a reference and develops an extended model by considering perceived trust, since the capabilities of blockchain technology for food traceability and transparency. The results show that blockchain technology has the capability to build trust and affect purchase intention. Results also highlight purchase intention is significantly and positively influenced by performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and habit. The results further show that technographic can significantly enhance intention to the use of blockchain technology to trace food. The research provides an insight to practitioners and researchers on how to increase intention towards blockchain.

Keywords- Blockchain ; Food traceability ; UTAUT2 ; Purchase intention.

I · INTRODUCTION

Fraud in the global food industry is a serious problem that has remained for years. Blockchain technology's potential to prevent fraud and strengthen security could fight agricultural fraud and improve food safety. Blockchain-based electronic supply chain ledger for tracking food from farm to shelf is channeled by some of the largest global retailers and suppliers. Consumers could scan the code in the store and convince themselves that they were buying exactly what they thought they were. The digital ledger records each step of a real transaction as. The application can also be accessed by and contains secure information that is up-to-date and easy to access.

Blockchain is an open, distributed ledger that can record transactions between two parties efficiently and in a verifiable and permanent way. Much of the initial private blockchain-based development is taking place in the

financial services sector, often within small networks of firms [1]. Moreover, much of the attention on blockchain today has focused on its ability to change the financial services industry fundamentally. The impact of blockchain technology goes beyond the financial sector [2].

Blockchain technology provides faster or less expensive transactions than those completed in traditional settings. Blockchain technology influence customer value by providing access to products or services that were previously not available or could only be garnered by expensing a large amount of time or money [3]. However, blockchain technology in food industry is still in its infancy stage, hence, there is a possibility that the service is seriously underutilized by customers thereby creating the need to address the issue.

A vast amount of information is being exchanged in blockchain-based electronic supply chain. This makes information more transparent. Perceived information transparency was not addressed in previous research studies as a determinant factor of blockchain adoption. Background knowledge comes from supply chain transparency in terms of how products were manufactured, stored, and delivered to customers [4] and can increase customers' trust by assuring the origin, authenticity, custody, and integrity of products [5]. This study examines influencing factors that affect consumers' purchase intent. The importance of the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology 2 (UTAUT2) model in different research context is highlighted by Venkatesh et al. (2012) [6]. This study proposes a theoretical model where the perceived trust is added as an extension to UTAUT2. Technographic segmentation is used to identify the behaviors and characteristics of customers. Consequently, in this study technographic is examined as an external factor that affects the beliefs related to blockchain. This approach is empirically tested through a quantitative study in the food industry, where blockchain technology has significant influence. This study is looking forward to providing blockchain technology with applicable guidelines for effectively implementing and designing blockchain application in food industry.

II · LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Many theoretical research models developed from psychology and sociology-related theories are being used in explaining technology acceptance and use. Use of Technology (UTAUT), substituted TAM in many studies. Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, and Davis [6] made the variables into four constructs: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and facilitating conditions. Performance expectancy is the degree to which it is beneficial to consumers in performing certain activities. Effort expectancy represents 'the degree of ease associated with the use of the system' [6]. Social influence is the 'degree to which individuals perceive that important others believe they should use the new system' [6]. Facilitating conditions refers to 'conceptualized knowledge, resources and opportunities to perform a specific behavior' [6]. UTAUT2 model was modified from UTAUT by adding hedonic motivation, price value and habit [7]. UTAUT2 has become well established and addresses the consumer context. This study extends UTAUT2 by including perceived trust concerns to investigate the purchase intention under the use of blockchain technology to trace food. The following research hypotheses are established:

H1

The performance expectancy (PE) in the use of blockchain technology to trace food has a positive influence on purchase intention (PI).

H2

The effort expectancy (EE) in the use of blockchain technology to trace food has a positive influence on purchase intention.

H3

The social influence (SI) regarding the use of blockchain technology to trace food has a positive influence on purchase intention.

H4

The facilitating conditions (FC) perceived in the use of blockchain technology to trace food have a positive influence on purchase intention.

H5

The hedonic motivation (HM) in the use of blockchain technology to trace food have a positive influence on purchase intention.

H6

The habit (HT) of using blockchain technology to trace food have a positive influence on purchase intention.

H7

The price value (PV) of using blockchain technology to trace food have a positive influence on purchase intention.

Past literatures have shown that trust has a significant influence on consumer's intention. Trust is a general attitude of optimism about the goodwill and capability of the exchange partner to fulfill claimed obligations [8]. In this sense, perceived trust was shown to impact the formation of long-term relationships and the formation of intent to purchase. [9].

When perceived trust is high, consumers are more likely to purchase and they are convinced that food data can be trust with blockchain technology. Therefore, it was hypothesized that:

H8

Perceived trust (PT) related to the use of blockchain technology to trace food have a positive influence on purchase intention.

Williams (2005) defines transparency 'using three features: relevant, timely and reliable information' [10]. Prior research also shows that consumers are increasingly being plagued by lack of information transparency. Information transparency has been recognized as a key factor affecting consumers' purchase behaviors [11]. Transparency creates a positive feeling among the general public which in turn fosters the development of trust. The relationship between the two variables has been discussed in previous studies [12]. Therefore, it was hypothesized that:

H9

Information transparency (IT) has positive influence on perceived trust related to the use of blockchain technology to trace food

The concept of technographics segmentation was first introduced in 1985 by Dr. Edward Forrest. Forrester provided technographics segmentation' as a marketing tool and this helps classify people according to how they use social technologies.

Some authors recognize the importance of taking attitude toward new technology as a benchmark to better understand consumers in such digital world [13]. Furthermore, according to Dr. Forrest's study, technographic has a positive relationship with intention to buy [14]. Following these assumptions, it can be hypothesized that:

H10a

Technographics (TG) has positive influence on the performance expectancy in the use of blockchain technology

H10b

Technographics has positive influence on the effort expectancy in the use of blockchain technology

H10c

Technogrphics has positive influence on the social influence regarding the use of blockchain technology

H10d

Technogrphics has positive influence on the facilitating conditions perceived in the use of blockchain technology

H10e

Technogrphics has positive influence on the hedonic motivation in the use of blockchain technology

H10f

Technogrphics has positive influence on the habit of using blockchain technology

H10g

Technogrphics has positive influence on the price of using blockchain technology.

Based on the review of the literature and hypotheses developed, the following model is proposed (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Research model

III. METHODOLOGY

The survey was carried out on those who are potential customer of using blockchain technology to trace food. The main survey lasts for around three weeks, and in total 264 samples were collected and analyzed

The measurement scales used for capturing data on the variables in the proposed model were adapted from prior literature. All items were measured on a five-point Likert scale anchored by 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Measurements for the core UTAUT2 variables (PE, EE, SI, FC, HM, HV and PV) were adapted from Venkatesh et al. [6]. The scale used for measuring trust was adapted from Ye, Shun, et al. (2019) [15], while that used for measuring technogrphics was adapted from Park, Jieun, et al (2013) [14] and Information transparency (IT) was adapted from Zhou, Liying, et al. (2018) [11]. The questionnaire also included background information such as age (measured in

years), gender (measured as a dummy variable with 0 for female and 1 otherwise), and formal education. All the participants are potential users of blockchain technology applications.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A. Descriptive statistics

Of the total sample, 53 % of respondents were female and 47 % were male (see Table 1). The majority of respondents fell in the age group of 21-30 (38.6%), followed by the group 31-40 (23.5 %). At least 77.7% of respondents had acquired a diploma, certificate or bachelor's degree.

Table1 Descriptive statistics of sample

Age Range	Male	Female	Total
<20	9	18	27
21-30	56	46	102
31-40	26	36	62
41-50	15	29	44
51-60	18	11	29
Grand Total	124	140	264

B. Measurement model

The model was tested using Smart PLS 3.0. Prior to testing the hypothesis, several quality criteria were used to evaluate the reliability (construct and indicator) and validity (convergent and discriminant) of the proposed model. Table 2 indicates the quality criteria used to evaluate the constructs which include Cronbach's alpha, average variance extracted (AVE), composite reliability (CR) and factor loadings. The average variance extracted for each variable was over .50, indicative of adequate convergence. The composite reliability was acceptable for each of the factors. Factor loadings were positive and statistically significant.

Table 2 Construct reliability and validity.

Construct	CR	AVE	Cronbach's α
PE	0.916	0.732	0.878
EE	0.921	0.745	0.886
SI	0.953	0.834	0.933
FC	0.877	0.642	0.815
HM	0.933	0.823	0.892
HT	0.961	0.861	0.946
PV	0.939	0.793	0.913
PI	0.938	0.834	0.900
IT	0.944	0.81	0.921
TG	0.937	0.832	0.899

PT	0.946	0.815	0.924
----	-------	-------	-------

This study compares AVE of each construct with the shared variance between constructs and if the square root of AVE is greater than the shared variance between constructs then the researcher can claim discriminant validity between constructs. Table 3 shows that discriminant validity exists in the model

Table 3 AVEs versus squares of correlations between constructs.

	EE	FC	HM	HT	TG	IT	PE	PV	SI	PT	PI
EE	(0.86)										
FC	0.790	(0.80)									
HM	0.695	0.692	(0.91)								
HT	0.532	0.454	0.607	(0.93)							
TG	0.555	0.567	0.568	0.511	(0.91)						
IT	0.716	0.727	0.675	0.383	0.511	(0.90)					
PE	0.662	0.650	0.672	0.483	0.449	0.691	(0.86)				
PV	0.651	0.615	0.663	0.525	0.414	0.616	0.677	(0.89)			
SI	0.636	0.613	0.695	0.588	0.468	0.524	0.639	0.655	(0.91)		
PT	0.663	0.673	0.679	0.518	0.518	0.795	0.595	0.656	0.566	(0.90)	
PI	0.704	0.635	0.635	0.562	0.556	0.678	0.619	0.606	0.520	0.665	(0.91)

C. The structural model

In the structural model, this study examine path coefficients and their significance levels. This study first computed the path coefficients with the entire sample by employing the bootstrapping method, and obtained the t-values corresponding to each path in the structural model. The results are shown in Table 4,

The explanatory power of the research model can be evaluated by examining the variance explained, or R² value of the final dependent construct. The PLS algorithm calculates the coefficient of determination, R², which is the proportion of the dependent variable explained by the influencing variables. R² for purchase intention is 0.612. R² for perceived trust is 0.632. Significance was determined by running the bootstrapping calculations. Twelve paths were significant as shown in Table 3

Table4 Significance of model paths

	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Significance
H1: PE -> PI	0.153	0.073	2.091	0.037	*
H2: EE -> PI	0.310	0.083	3.748	0.000	***
H3: SI -> PI	-0.131	0.072	1.810	0.071	NS
H4: FC -> PI	0.050	0.084	0.597	0.551	NS
H5: HM -> PI	0.060	0.074	0.805	0.421	NS
H6: HT -> PI	0.189	0.065	2.919	0.004	**
H7: PV -> PI	0.068	0.075	0.905	0.366	NS

H8: PT -> PI	0.226	0.073	3.097	0.002	**
H9: IT -> PT	0.795	0.026	30.132	0.000	***
H10a: TG -> PE	0.449	0.051	8.882	0.000	***
H10b: TG -> EE	0.555	0.052	10.712	0.000	***
H10c: TG -> SI	0.468	0.054	8.639	0.000	***
H10d: TG -> FC	0.567	0.047	12.073	0.000	***
H10e: TG -> HM	0.568	0.054	10.543	0.000	***
H10f: TG -> HT	0.511	0.052	9.858	0.000	***
H10g: TG -> PV	0.414	0.056	7.361	0.000	***

V · DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A. Outcome of hypotheses

The hypothesized relationships were evaluated using the structural model presented in Fig.1. A total of 16 hypotheses were developed in this study. Based on the findings, it 12 hypothesis (H1, H2, H6, H8, H9 and H10a, b, c, d, e, f, g) were supported while 4 (H3, H4, H5, H7) were not supported.

Hypothesis H1 suggested a positive and significant association between performance expectancy and purchase intention. The findings also showed H2 as effort expectancy has a significant association with purchase intention. The findings support Jaradat and Rababaa [24] who showed that effort expectancy was significant in predicting the intention to adopt m-commerce. This study found support for the association between information transparency and perceived trust thus supporting hypothesis H9, which is in line with prior studies [12]. In this study, habit influences purchase intention regarding prior food traceability use. As prior studies, habit is a strong predictor of future technology use [25]. Also, outcome of technographics was expected as it is strongly in line with prior studies on purchase intention [14]. Perceived trust was found to have the highest influence on purchase intention, thus supporting the need for including trust as an added factor in the UTAUT2 [26].

B. Practical implications

As seen from the results of this study and the growing literature on blockchain, it is increasingly evident that different factors influence blockchain technology adoption in different applications. This study identified two key factors that blockchain technology must focus on trust and value. Consumers who wish to engage in mobile commerce want to receive value. They enjoy saving time and being able to look for products at any time/any place [27]. Practitioners need to exploit individual's intrinsic motivation in technology environments. Blockchain technology enables distributed public ledgers that hold immutable data in a secure and encrypted way and ensure that transactions can

never be altered. Cheaper cost and a faster confirmation process need to be considered in blockchain application.

C. Conclusion

The recent upsurge of technology use amongst individuals in non-organizational context has led to consumer-focused research model such as extended unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT2) [28]. This study makes a theoretical contribution by showing that adding perceived trust to the current UTAUT2 model improves its effectiveness in predicting. The study also contributed to the limited literature the advocates technographics segmentation for considering classifying people according to how they use technologies. Consumer technographics provides broad views of customer behaviors and adoption and use patterns, allowing business to better understand and anticipate consumer actions and expectations.

Food fraud is a challenge in food industry. The trace module enables effective management and food safety across entire food system. However, customers still have little or no knowledge about blockchain technology. Blockchain suppliers should focus on improving customers knowledge on the benefits of blockchain applications.

D. Limitations of the study

This study presents a important attempt an understanding the phenomenon of blockchain, the study also has some limitations. Firstly, researchers have cautioned that when respondents have not had enough experience with a given technology [26]. Blockchain is still low, thus most respondents had little or no experience with the technology. Secondly, the study was conducted with consumers of Taiwan. Future research can implement it in other countries and compare findings.

REFERENCES

- [1] Iansiti, Marco, and Karim R. Lakhani. "The truth about blockchain." *Harvard Business Review* 95.1 (2017): 118-127.
- [2] Hughes, Alex, et al. "Beyond Bitcoin: What blockchain and distributed ledger technologies mean for firms." *Business Horizons* (2019).
- [3] Morkunas, Vida J., Jeannette Paschen, and Edward Boon. "How blockchain technologies impact your business model." *Business Horizons* (2019).
- [4] Kietzmann, Jan, and Ana Canhoto. "Bittersweet! Understanding and managing electronic word of mouth." *Journal of Public Affairs* 13.2 (2013): 146-159.
- [5] Montecchi, Matteo, Kirk Plangger, and Michael Etter. "It's real, trust me! Establishing supply chain provenance using blockchain." *Business Horizons* (2019).
- [6] Venkatesh, Viswanath, et al. "User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view." *MIS quarterly* (2003): 425-478.
- [7] Venkatesh, Viswanath, James YL Thong, and Xin Xu. "Consumer acceptance and use of information technology: extending the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology." *MIS quarterly* 36.1 (2012): 157-178.
- [8] Schurr, Paul H., and Julie L. Ozanne. "Influences on exchange processes: Buyers' preconceptions of a seller's trustworthiness and bargaining toughness." *Journal of consumer research* 11.4 (1985): 939-953.
- [9] Hsin Chang, Hsin, and Su Wen Chen. "The impact of online store environment cues on purchase intention: Trust and perceived risk as a mediator." *Online information review* 32.6 (2008): 818-841.
- [10] Williams, Cynthia Clark. "Trust diffusion: The effect of interpersonal trust on structure, function, and organizational transparency." *Business & Society* 44.3 (2005): 357-368.
- [11] Zhou, Liying, et al. "Perceived information transparency in B2C e-commerce: An empirical investigation." *Information & Management* 55.7 (2018): 912-927
- [12] Nunkoo, Robin, et al. "Public trust in mega event planning institutions: The role of knowledge, transparency and corruption." *Tourism Management* 66 (2018): 155-166.
- [13] Bernhoff, Josh, Shelley Morrisette, and Kenneth Clemmer. "Technographics Service Explained." *Forrester Report* 1.0 (1998):1.
- [14] Park, Jieun, et al. "Driver's intention to use smartphone-car connectivity." (2013).
- [15] Ye, Shun, et al. "Enhancing customer trust in peer-to-peer accommodation: A "soft" strategy via social presence." *International Journal of Hospitality Management* 79 (2019): 1-10.
- [16] Ding, W. and Marchionini, G. 1997. *A Study on Video Browsing Strategies*. Technical Report. University of Maryland at College Park.
- [17] Fröhlich, B. and Plate, J. 2000. The cubic mouse: a new device for three-dimensional input. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (The Hague, The Netherlands, April 01 - 06, 2000). CHI '00. ACM, New York, NY, 526-531. DOI= <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/332040.332491>.
- [18] Tavel, P. 2007. *Modeling and Simulation Design*. AK Peters Ltd., Natick, MA.
- [19] Sannella, M. J. 1994. *Constraint Satisfaction and Debugging for Interactive User Interfaces*. Doctoral Thesis. UMI Order Number: UMI Order No. GAX95-09398., University of Washington.
- [20] Forman, G. 2003. An extensive empirical study of feature selection metrics for text classification. *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 3 (Mar. 2003), 1289-1305.
- [21] Brown, L. D., Hua, H., and Gao, C. 2003. A widget framework for augmented interaction in SCAPE. In *Proceedings of the 16th Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology* (Vancouver, Canada, November 02 - 05, 2003). UIST '03. ACM, New York, NY, 1-10. DOI= <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/964696.964697>.
- [22] Yu, Y. T. and Lau, M. F. 2006. A comparison of MC/DC, MUMCUT and several other coverage criteria for logical decisions. *J. Syst. Softw.* 79, 5 (May. 2006), 577-590. DOI= <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2005.05.030>.
- [23] Spector, A. Z. 1989. Achieving application requirements. In *Distributed Systems*, S. Mullender, Ed. ACM Press Frontier Series. ACM, New York, NY, 19-33. DOI= <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/90417.90738>.
- [24] Jaradat, Mohammed-Issa Riad Mousa, and Mamoun S. Al Rababaa. "Assessing key factor that influence on the acceptance of mobile commerce based on modified UTAUT." *International Journal of Business and Management* 8.23 (2013): 102.
- [25] Kim, Sung S., and Naresh K. Malhotra. "A longitudinal model of continued IS use: An integrative view of four mechanisms underlying postadoption phenomena." *Management science* 51.5 (2005): 741-755.
- [26] Verkijika, Silas Formunyuy. "Factors influencing the adoption of mobile commerce applications in Cameroon." *Telematics and Informatics* 35.6 (2018): 1665-1674.
- [27] Shaw, Norman, and Ksenia Sergueeva. "The non-monetary benefits of mobile commerce: Extending UTAUT2 with perceived value." *International Journal of Information Management* 45 (2019): 44-55.
- [28] Tamilmani, Kuttimani, et al. "The battle of Brain vs. Heart: A literature review and meta-analysis of "hedonic motivation" use in

UTAUT2." *International Journal of Information Management* 46
(2019): 222-235.